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Electronic Health Record data interoperability and reuse: Towards using Clinical Quality Language to evaluate Health and Care Information models

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Abstract

Introduction The European Health Data Space (EHDS) requires all EU countries to comply with interoperability requirements in healthcare. The Netherlands is moving toward the adoption of common standards to support consistent and reusable health data, including HL7 Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR), openEHR, and Health and Care Information Models (HCIMs). HCIMs provide abstract models of clinical concepts with the aim of contributing to interoperability and (re)usability in the healthcare landscape of the Netherlands, but their practical implementation remains underexplored. In this thesis, the use of Clinical Quality Language (CQL), an HL7 standard aligned with FHIR, to evaluate the use of HCIMs in practice is explored.

Methods A framework for applying CQL to evaluate HCIMs in practice was developed, containing an assessment of the suitability of CQL for this purpose, two use scenarios to guide practical application, an evaluation focus, a structured method for formulating tests, and illustrative examples demonstrating its use. Furthermore, a test environment was built to enable HCIM evaluation with CQL, using open-source tools, including HAPI FHIR, CQF Ruler, Synthea, and the Dutch National Terminology Server. Finally, a multidisciplinary working group formulated and grouped CQL tests for the HCIM 'Allergy Intolerance.'

Results The results include a framework for the use of CQL to evaluate HCIMs in practice. CQL proved to be suitable for verifying the presence of required data elements, specific relationships between those elements, correct data types, and the use of specific value sets. Within the obtained framework, CQL tests are used to make a comparison between the actual result and the expected result. This either evaluates HCIM compliance, how well the practical situation adheres to an HCIM, or HCIM alignment, how well the HCIM represents usage in practice. Furthermore, a test environment is built using components for executing CQL (CQF Ruler), storing test data and CQL libraries (HAPI FHIR), hosting terminology (Dutch National Terminology Server), generating synthetic patient data (Synthea), and interacting with system APIs (Postman). Various CQL tests are developed based on the HCIM 'Allergy Intolerance' to demonstrate the use of the defined framework.

Discussion The contribution of this work is threefold, including the development of an initial framework for applying CQL in HCIM evaluation, validation of its technical feasibility through testing in a test environment, and exploration of its practical applicability and potential for generalization across different HCIMs. CQL was selected for its alignment with HL7 FHIR, human readability, and abilities for modular and reusable logic, making it suitable for broad (national) implementation. The proposed approach complements ongoing initiatives like the NFU Monitor and BgZ-audit by providing insight into the semantic and structural correctness of health data. Other than evaluating HCIMs in practice, agreements recorded in other models, such as FHIR, openEHR, and XtEHR models, could be tested in a similar way. Usage in practice depends on the support for CQL execution, availability of a FHIR server, and national library development and maintenance. The EHDS's push for interoperability may encourage greater use of FHIR servers, potentially simplifying CQL execution across systems.

Conclusion In this thesis, it is illustrated how CQL could serve as a practical tool to systematically evaluate the implementation of HCIMs, offering a bridge between conceptual standards and practice. CQL can be used to evaluate the practical implementation of HCIMs in the Netherlands by providing a reusable evaluation framework, enabling systematic testing through a technical setup in practice, and supporting reusability through the development and maintenance of generalizable CQL libraries. The results of this thesis show that it is possible to create a systematic method for testing. They also outline necessary components for the technical setup and suggest that tests for HCIM evaluation are generalizable.

List of abbreviations

BL	Boolean	17
CD	Concept Descriptions	17
CDS	Clinical Decision Support	16
CO	Codable Original	17
CQF	Clinical Quality Framework	16
CQL	Clinical Quality Language	6
CQM	Clinical Quality Measurement	16
DCM	Detailed Clinical Model	12
ED	Encoded Data	17
EHDS	European Health Data Space	6
EHR	Electronic Health Record	6
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interpretable, and Reusable	10
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources	6
HCIM	Health and Care Information Model	6
HL7	Health Level 7	6
II	Instance Identifier	17
INT	Integer Number	17
LOINC	Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Code	13
PQ	Physical Quantity	17
SNOMED CT	Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine - Clinical Terminology	13
ST	String	17
TS	Time Stamp	17
UCUM	Unified Code for Units of Measure	13

1 General Introduction

With the entry of the European Health Data Space (EHDS) on 18 March 2025, the pursuit of data availability to improve healthcare is laid down in law, obliging all countries in the EU to meet interoperability requirements gradually, following a timeline that extends to 2031 [1]. Data availability involves having recorded health data accessible, reachable, and usable for specific information needs [2]. Three commonly recognized standards in the Netherlands are Health Level 7 (HL7) Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) [3], openEHR [4], and Health and Care Information Models (HCIMs). FHIR defines data formats and exchange protocols for Electronic Health Records (EHRs), while openEHR focuses on structured clinical data and modeling for longitudinal health records. The HCIMs, or *Zorginformatiebouwstenen (Zibs)* in Dutch, were introduced in 2013, with the aim to improve interoperability and reuse in the healthcare landscape of the Netherlands. This applies to all forms of (re)use, independent of care processes and use cases, with explicit safeguards for patient safety and privacy. True availability of healthcare data enables more efficient and higher-quality care delivery while supporting innovation.

HCIMs are used to achieve consistent documentation and (re)use of healthcare information, aiming to contribute to the standardization of healthcare data. An HCIM describes which healthcare information needs to be recorded for a particular concept and how [5]. It defines a clinical concept in a manner that enables its (re)use as a building block across various healthcare situations and information systems [6]. They are more abstract than international standards like HL7 FHIR [3], which defines data formats and exchange protocols for electronic health records (EHRs), and openEHR [4], which focuses on structured clinical data and modeling for longitudinal health records. Rather than specifying the technologies to be used, HCIMs operate at a more conceptual level. They build on top of such standards, guiding how the healthcare landscape should be modeled in a way that fits the national context. The Dutch healthcare sector has started working with HCIMs since 2013, and now a community-based initiative is underway called the HCIM transition, or *zib-transitie* in Dutch, to improve the effective use of HCIMs in the Netherlands [7].

Developing these abstract models is already a complex task, and it becomes even more challenging when their real-world impact remains unclear. Despite the considerable effort invested in the construction of HCIMs, relatively little attention has been paid to how they are used in clinical settings. We propose using Clinical Quality Language (CQL), an HL7 standard to express clinical logic and queries within EHRs and other healthcare systems, to bridge this gap [8]. While CQL is already used for population-level measurements, its potential for evaluating the practical use of HCIMs is still unexplored. Since CQL can operate on FHIR repositories, it aligns well with the Netherlands' adoption of HL7 FHIR as the national standard for healthcare data exchange. By using CQL to check whether data fields from HCIMs are populated as expected, we can start to assess how well these models are implemented in practice.

In this thesis, the first steps are taken towards understanding how the consistency of data registration with the use of HCIMs can be evaluated using CQL. The aim is to gain insight into how the consistency of data registration with the use of HCIMs can be evaluated with CQL. The main question is: "How can CQL be used to evaluate the practical implementation of HCIMs in the Netherlands?" This thesis is structured around three sub-questions, each addressed in a dedicated chapter. The sub-questions and their corresponding chapters are presented in Figure 1. These chapters follow a consistent structure, including an introduction, methods, results, discussion, and conclusion.

<p>Main Question How can CQL be used to evaluate the practical implementation of HCIMs in the Netherlands?</p>
<p><i>Chapter 4</i> Using CQL for a different purpose: Identifying an application of CQL to evaluate HCIMs How can a framework be formulated to apply CQL for evaluating the implementation of HCIMs in practice?</p>
<p><i>Chapter 5</i> From identification to demonstration: Establishing a test environment for evaluating HCIMs with CQL How can a test environment be designed to demonstrate the application of CQL in evaluating HCIM implementation?</p>
<p><i>Chapter 6</i> Illustrative example of the application: CQL to evaluate the HCIM 'Allergy Intolerance' What concrete CQL test cases can be developed to evaluate the implementation of the HCIM 'Allergy Intolerance'?</p>

Figure 1: Main research question and sub-research questions.

Chapters 2 and 3 lay a foundation by briefly describing the healthcare landscape in the Netherlands, focusing on data availability, relevant governance factors, and common healthcare standards. Chapters 4, 5, and 6 address the sub-questions. They present the initial framework for using CQL to evaluate HCIMs, describe the developed test environment to assess technical feasibility, and validate the test development method of the framework by applying it to one HCIM. Finally, the general discussion and conclusion summarize the overall findings and offer a concluding reflection on the thesis as a whole.

2 Data availability

Healthcare in the Netherlands is structured in a way that citizens receive care from different healthcare providers and at different locations. As a result, patient information is recorded in different places, making it difficult for people to keep track of all their medical data and for healthcare providers to quickly access those data [9]. Bringing together data from different silos takes time and important information can be lost. A more effective approach is to ensure that the data is accessible when needed, with proper authorization.

2.1 From data exchange to data availability

Data exchange and data availability are frequently used terms in the context of data management in healthcare, but they have different meanings. Data exchange refers to the process of sharing data between different systems or healthcare providers, such as transferring patient information between a hospital and a general practitioner [10]. It focuses on the direct transfer of data between parties and is typically limited to the care process, being used within a single care pathway or among directly involved healthcare providers.

Definition of data exchange:

Data exchange is the transfer of information between different systems or healthcare providers. [2].

Data availability goes beyond just exchanging data. It refers to the ability to access and use data when needed, specifically focusing on the availability of data within a particular system or network [10]. It means that data can be accessed and used when needed, regardless of where it is stored or what system manages it. This eliminates the need for double documentation, which occurs with data exchange or lack of interoperability, where information is being duplicated rather than reused [11, 12]. Data availability is crucial for any form of (re)use, whether in primary or secondary processes, regardless of the care setting or the specific use case.

Definition of data availability:

Data availability includes having recorded health data available, accessible, and usable for the specific information need. It applies to all forms of (re)use, independent of care processes and use cases, with explicit guarantees for patient safety and privacy [2].

Currently, citizens cannot obtain an integrated picture of their own health data, as it is scattered across various systems. Data availability will enable citizens to take control of managing their own health data, as lack of availability currently hinders them from overseeing their care process. Moreover, data availability is also useful to stimulate innovation through research. Researchers must spend time finding, interpreting and preparing data [13]. Standardizing health data and metadata can streamline this process, allowing researchers to spend their time and resources on actual research. Data availability will make health data accessible to citizens, healthcare providers, and for research, innovation, prevention, and policy [2].

To achieve optimal data availability, healthcare information should be uniformly structured and consistently applied across various use cases [14]. HCIMs provide a way to establish agreements on standardized language in the field of healthcare information. More information about HCIM is provided in Section ??.

2.2 Main aspects of data availability

Data availability can be divided into three main aspects: availability of data, accessibility of data, and usability of data [2]. Figure 2 displays all components in more detail.

Data Availability	Availability of Data	Registration: Data should be registered once according to standards. This prevents double registrations and increases accuracy.
		Provision: Data from all relevant sources should be available to all stakeholders, with the citizen having as much control as possible.
		Presence: Data should be up-to-date and immediately usable for the care process.
	Accessibility of Data	Findable: Data should be quickly searchable through metadata and generic functions such as localization and addressing.
		Consent: Access to data should be well-regulated through generic functions, identification, authentication, and authorization, with attention to privacy and security.
		Transport: A nationwide infrastructure for data availability and standards such as FHIR ensures that data is shared securely and efficiently between systems.
	Usability of Data	Unity of Language: Standardized terminology, such as SNOMED and LOINC, ensures that data is consistent and understandable for both humans and machines.
		Context: Data should include contextual information such as metadata, source, author, date, and time of registration.
		Data Quality: High-quality data at the source is essential and requires collaboration and trust between involved parties.

Figure 2: Main aspects of data availability [2].

2.3 Interoperability

Interoperability is the ability of two or more systems to work together despite differences in language, interface, execution platform, and technologies adopted [15]. The Healthcare Information and Management Systems Society (HIMSS), an international advisor supporting the transformation of the health ecosystem, has defined four levels of interoperability: foundational, structural, semantic, and organizational [16]. The foundational level refers to the requirements for secure data exchange between systems. The structural level contains the format and syntax necessary for correct data interpretation. The semantic level includes shared models and standardized definitions to ensure common understanding. Finally, the organizational level is about governance, policy, and legal considerations to facilitate seamless data use between entities. The primary goal of HCIMs is to achieve semantic interoperability, or unity of language, in the field of healthcare data [17] This is essential for effective communication across the boundaries of healthcare institutions and even between different healthcare sectors.

Definition of semantic interoperability:

Semantic interoperability is the ability to share data among organizations or systems while ensuring data is understood and interpreted regardless of who is involved, using domain concepts, context knowledge, and formal data representation [18].

2.4 The layer framework

The management of information within the field of healthcare is complex due to the numerous responsibilities and interests involved. Recognizing that proper and consistent analysis, discussion, and design require structure, the layer framework for information solutions was developed specifically for this purpose within the healthcare domain [19]. The framework, displayed in Figure 3, consists of five layers [20]:

- **Organization policy** defines organizational collaboration among healthcare providers, including roles, responsibilities, and authority at a managerial level.
- **Care process** focuses on collaborative care processes, including integration points and transfer moments among healthcare organizations, set by professionals and managers.
- **Information** specifies the information to be recorded and shared during care transfer moments, agreed upon by healthcare and information professionals.
- **Application** concerns healthcare information systems, specifying relevant systems for information processing and exchange, determined by IT professionals and application managers.
- **IT-infrastructure** involves the technical infrastructure supporting information systems, including networks, servers, and databases, facilitating secure information exchange set by IT specialists.

For optimal interoperability, data handling across all layers must comply with legal requirements, ensuring security measures for information availability, exclusivity, and integrity [19]. OpenEHR and FHIR can be positioned at the application level. The HCIMs can be placed at the information level together with the corresponding terminology. They provide a way to describe healthcare processes in a structured way so that it can be applied uniformly at the application level.

Figure 3: Layer framework from Nictiz [19].

2.5 FAIR data

The Findable, Accessible, Interpretable, and Reusable (FAIR) principles play a role in enabling data availability. To maximize the value of EHRs, it is necessary that the data is interoperable and reusable without loss of original meaning and context. This is also where the FAIR principles stand for [21].

- **Findable:** To ensure that data is findable, they must be assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier and described with rich metadata. Metadata should clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe, and both data and metadata should be registered or indexed in a searchable resource.
- **Accessible:** For data to be accessible, they must be retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol, which is open, free, and universally implementable, and allows for authentication and authorization procedures where necessary. Even when the data is no longer available, the metadata must remain accessible.
- **Interoperable:** To be interoperable, (meta)data should utilize a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation, and use vocabularies that adhere to FAIR principles, including qualified references to other (meta)data.
- **Reusable:** Finally, to be reusable, (meta)data must be richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes, be released with a clear and accessible data usage license, associated with detailed provenance, and conform to domain-relevant community standards.

How the FAIR principles relate to the work in this thesis is elaborated on in Section 7.5, as part of the General Discussion.

2.6 Key forces driving data availability in the Netherlands

The healthcare system in the Netherlands is governed by laws, regulations, and policy agreements. To understand what is currently playing in the legal and regulatory part of the five-layer framework, we examine four influential laws. Legislation and regulations such as the *Wet elektronische gegevensuitwisseling in de zorg (Wegiz)* and the EHDS, as well as agreements and policy initiatives such as the *Intergraal zorgakkoord (IZA)* and the *nationale visie en strategie (NVS)* form the basis for standardized, secure and effective exchange of data in the coming years and underline the importance of data availability in healthcare. The *Wegiz* and *IZA* specifically focus on the primary use of healthcare data, while the *NVS* and *EHDS* also include the secondary use of healthcare data. These regulations advocate for better data availability and modeling of health information.

2.6.1 Wegiz

Since the implementation of the *Wegiz* on July 1, 2023, the electronic exchange of data in five data exchanges has been made mandatory and standardized [22]. The *Wegiz*, or electronic data interchange in healthcare act, is a framework law, meaning that additional rules will be introduced stating which data exchanges must take place electronically and from when. With *Wegiz*, the Netherlands is well on track in implementing the EHDS to improve electronic data exchange in healthcare [23]. Some fundamentals from the *Wegiz* which are also part of the EHDS include realizing national ICT infrastructure that enables interoperability and standardizing the exchange of data [24]. This ensures that information is registered and exchanged uniformly, providing all healthcare providers with access to the same relevant information.

2.6.2 NVS

The NVS, or national vision and strategy, is built on three fundamental pillars: data availability, trust, and governance [2]. The NVS has four guiding principles relating to the health information system [2]:

- **Availability of data:** Data is available to all those involved in a care network and to the citizens themselves.
- **Secondary use:** Data is available for secondary use, with minimal registration burden for healthcare providers.
- **Focus on application:** Data is separated from functionality.
- **Stimulating innovation:** The health information system creates an open market that stimulates innovation.

The NVS provides direction for making decisions about how the information system can support and facilitate changes in healthcare [25]. Ultimately, the NVS aims to ensure that citizens can participate in decisions about their care with all the necessary data available to them. It also aims to equip healthcare providers with the right data to offer better and safer care, as well as more opportunities to promote health. Additionally, researchers and policymakers can use the available data to increase knowledge and provide well-founded and effective guidance.

2.6.3 IZA

The IZA, or integrated care agreement, aims to ensure that healthcare remains high quality, accessible, and affordable for the future [26]. To achieve this, agreements have been made between the Ministry of Health, Welfare, and Sport, or *Ministerie van Volksgezondheid, Welzijn en Sport (VWS)*, and a wide range of stakeholders in the healthcare sector. Signatories of the IZA include umbrella organizations representing hospitals, mental healthcare, and elderly care. The IZA emphasizes the importance of appropriate, hybrid care and regional cooperation. Crucial here is the availability and clarity of care data so that it can also be shared between care providers and with patients [14].

2.6.4 EHDS

While not yet implemented, the EHDS is already influencing policy making in the Netherlands. The EHDS is part of the European data strategy, based on the Data Governance Act and the EU Data Act, focusing specifically on healthcare [27]. It aims to establish a robust infrastructure and governance model to improve the interoperability of health data across Europe, improve patient care, and promote scientific research, innovation, and policy [28]. The EHDS strives for better data availability and promotes better exchange and access to different health data types [29, 30]. Furthermore, it intends to create a situation in which patients have more control over their electronic health data while allowing healthcare providers to focus more on patient care [24]. By 2031, all healthcare information systems within the European Union (EU) must meet interoperability requirements, facilitating information exchange within and between healthcare institutions and ensuring that all data is shared with patients and healthcare providers [24]. The EHDS gives countries in the EU the flexibility to tailor implementation to their own healthcare landscape. In the Netherlands, the NVS assists with this adapted implementation [23].

3 Navigating healthcare standards: DCM, OpenEHR, HL7 FHIR, HCIM, SNOMED CT, LOINC

Achieving data availability and semantic interoperability requires the coordinated use of different types of standards. This section describes some relevant standards based on Detailed Clinical Model (DCM), common terminologies, and how these components relate to each other.

3.1 DCM and two-level modeling

The idea of the DCM paradigm is to separate knowledge and information, creating a concept model that is flexible and software-independent [31]. This paradigm is also known as two-level modeling or dual-model methodology. On one side, it defines a reference model that contains essential components and constraints required for the development of a standardized EHR. On the other side, it introduces an archetype model to formalize clinical-domain concepts in alignment with the reference model. To have a complete semantic representation, formally defined information models are linked to standard terminologies [32]. This contributes to interoperability and data reuse without loss of meaning or context [33]. The most relevant DCM-based standards in the context of the healthcare landscape in the Netherlands are openEHR, FHIR, and HCIMs, with openEHR and FHIR being international standards and HCIMs being a national standard. Regarding the layer framework, FHIR and openEHR can be positioned at the application level, while HCIMs sit at the information level along with the corresponding terminologies.

3.1.1 OpenEHR

Based on the dual-model methodology, openEHR is an open-source specification for a vendor-neutral platform designed to manage EHR data in a structured and standardized way [34]. To structure and standardize health data, archetypes and templates are used. They are clinical models that define reusable patterns for representing clinical concepts and can be applied separately.

Archetypes Archetypes are structured models that add domain-specific semantics to information models, allowing for meaningful data representation without causing excessive growth and complexity in the underlying models [35]. They help define reusable patterns for organizing data in fields like healthcare, ensuring consistency and interoperability across different systems while keeping the core information model stable [35].

Templates Templates are structured specifications that define how multiple archetypes are combined to form complete data sets for specific use cases, such as clinical documents or reports [36]. They provide a way to tailor archetypes to local needs, ensuring consistency in data capture, validation, and exchange while maintaining alignment with standardized information models [36].

3.1.2 HL7 FHIR

HL7 FHIR defines the data format and the communication protocol for exchanging medical information between different computer systems, ensuring interoperability regardless of how data is stored [37]. FHIR is increasingly used by healthcare IT providers in the Netherlands, sometimes in combination with openEHR [38]. To ensure semantic consistency and adaptability to local contexts, FHIR allows the structuring of data through the use of resources and profiles.

Resources Resources are modular components that represent specific healthcare concepts. Each has a unique identity, belonging to a specific resource type, containing structured data elements, and maintaining versioning to track content changes [39].

Profiles Profiles allow for customizing resources to meet specific requirements by applying a set of limitations and/or extensions [40]. They can be based on national-specific models such as HCIMs [41].

3.1.3 HCIMs

HCIMs do not define how data should be exchanged or stored. They are used to establish agreements about language unity in the field of DCM [17]. HCIMs are information models of minimal clinical concepts, each of which contains multiple data elements with agreed-upon content, structure, and mutual relationships. Within an HCIM, a healthcare concept is described in terms of the data elements that make up that concept, and the data types of those elements.

Definition of an HCIM:

An HCIM is a model of related data elements that, as a whole, describes a clinical concept, defining how the data elements in a system within a process can be recorded to enable semantic interoperability, especially if that data element needs to be available in other processes and associated systems [42, 43].

Standardization in clinical modeling is necessary for good reuse of information in healthcare and to ensure that the receiving system understands the information in the same way as the sending system intended, achieving semantic interoperability [14]. HCIMs are designed to standardize how and what information needs to be registered in the healthcare process to increase semantic interoperability [7]. Nictiz, the Dutch knowledge center for national applications of ICT in healthcare, develops HCIMs for the Netherlands. The organization is mostly financed by the Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport, *Ministerie van Gezondheid, Welzijn en Sport (VWS)* [44].

Since 2013, the Netherlands has used HCIMs as a standard for uniform modeling of healthcare information [14]. They contain specifications for functional content, forming a basis for further technical specifications and elaborations at the application level [45]. HCIMs facilitate these follow-up goals but do not elaborate on them. An HCIM is aimed at (re)usability and does not contain agreements that only apply to one specific healthcare situation. Agreements focusing on use-case-specific applications of HCIMs are recorded within information standards, while HCIMs are not suitable for direct implementation [45].

Information standards The dataset of an information standard contains the specification of all data (clinical concepts) that are recorded or exchanged within the context of a specific care process and defined use case(s) [43].

3.2 Terminologies

3.2.1 SNOMED CT

Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine – Clinical Terminology (SNOMED CT) is an international medical terminology system aimed at recording clinical findings and procedures. It contains a vast collection of medical terms and their synonyms, used in direct patient care to record various clinical information [46]. Managed by SNOMED International, the terms are originally in English, but relevant parts have been translated into several languages, including Dutch, Danish, German, French, Spanish, and Swedish. Healthcare providers use SNOMED CT to record essential patient information such as diagnoses, medication use, interventions, and treatment plans. The system offers advantages, including comprehensive, scientifically validated content, detailed coding of medical data, and integration with other international standards [47]. Used in over forty countries, SNOMED CT helps reduce administrative burdens within healthcare institutions.

3.2.2 LOINC

Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Code (LOINC) is an international coding system that aims to standardize concepts of laboratory requests, laboratory results, and clinical terms [48]. LOINC is managed by Regenstrief International and is also recognized in the Netherlands as an important building block for interoperability in healthcare. It facilitates an unambiguous representation of observations, with laboratory determinations as the priority. A LOINC code refers to six fields that define a measurement or observation. These fields are: component, property, timing, system, scale, and method [48]. The use of LOINC leads to standardized exchange and availability of laboratory determinations and results, across the boundaries of user groups (laboratories, general practitioners, hospitals, pharmacies) and countries [49]. The *Nederlandse Labcodeset*, or Dutch lab code set, serves as a subset of the international LOINC database. It is enhanced with Unified Code for Units of Measure (UCUM), which allows for standardized recording of units of measurement, and SNOMED CT [49].

3.3 Overview of the standards

With several common standards introduced that shape the healthcare landscape of the Netherlands, their interrelations will be described now. First, the international standards openEHR and FHIR are compared, followed by a description of the role of the nationally defined HCIMs. Furthermore, the terminologies SNOMED CT and LOINC are compared. Finally, a brief overview of all these standards is given.

3.3.1 Comparing openEHR and FHIR

It is important to make a technical distinction between the processing and sharing of healthcare information. This distinction is useful when comparing openEHR and FHIR. Figure 4, adapted from Alastair Allen [50], illustrates where the focus of openEHR and FHIR lies, with the base of each triangle representing the strength of each standard. This does not imply that the narrow end of the triangle is weak, but rather that the focus is more on the other parts.

Figure 4: Comparison between openEHR and FHIR. Adapted from Alastair Allen [50].

The wider base of the triangle for openEHR reflects its strong capabilities in data processing and storage, while the wider base for FHIR highlights its strength in facilitating interoperability and data exchange [50]. They are more efficient in different areas, making them complement each other well. It is not about using one or the other, but rather a combination of the two to avoid potential compromises. The announced collaboration between the two will enhance the ability to use them together effectively.

3.3.2 Role of HCIMs

With FHIR facilitating the exchange of information and openEHR facilitating the recording of information, what role do HCIMs play? The idea of HCIMs is to improve the ability to align with the healthcare situation in the Netherlands closely [38, 51], representing it more precisely than any international standard could. They focus on accurately reflecting the local healthcare environment, regardless of the current state or progress of international standards, securing the Dutch healthcare situation in logical models.

HCIMs were introduced in the Netherlands at a time when there was a need to model the healthcare situation from the field. During the mapping from HCIMs to FHIR profiles, imperfections were discovered in FHIR resources and HCIMs. Issues were filed by FHIR specialists in the Netherlands to HL7 and to HCIM developers, helping to improve them both. A lot has changed since then. FHIR resources better reflect how the healthcare sector should be modeled, and FHIR is increasingly used nationally and internationally. In addition, openEHR is being recognized as a solution for storing and retaining data.

Right now, it is a challenge to map data elements from FHIR to openEHR or the other way around. With the announced collaboration, it is expected that things will change and that FHIR and openEHR will align more closely. These changes also influence the view at HCIMs, and together with the demand for improvements, the HCIM transition is focusing on constructing HCIMs 2.0. Apart from the shift in the purposes that HCIMs must fulfill and how they fit into healthcare care, HCIMs are constantly evolving to best align with healthcare care processes as they can change. Value sets are also dynamic for this reason.

The HCIMs are implemented through a translation to FHIR profiles. These FHIR profiles of HCIMs are defined to provide a standard way of this translation, as different choices can be made in this process. In the Netherlands, three levels of FHIR profiles are recognized: HCIM profiles, NL core profiles, and information standard specific profiles. The HCIM profiles represent a certain HCIM as best as possible [52]. NL core profiles are derived from an

HCIM and might have been enriched by concepts from different use cases that apply the HCIM [52]. Information standard specific profiles are derived from the NL core profiles, further restricting or enhancing these profiles for a particular use case [52].

FHIR and openEHR do not offer a direct application for Dutch healthcare and do not make agreements on the application of terminologies [14]. Within HCIMs, agreements are made about when and how (international) terminologies or value sets are used. Although international terminologies such as SNOMED CT and LOINC provide good coverage, adjustments and specific agreements are often necessary regarding their use within the Dutch context. Similarly, many value sets are either based on or adapted from international standards to meet local requirements. Standardizing the use of these terminologies and value sets specific to the Netherlands within HCIMs can help ensure consistency beyond the scope of international standards.

Moreover, HCIMs function independently of technical implementations, providing a clear and consistent description of clinical concepts [14]. FHIR and openEHR also use clinical models as a basis, each developed in a format for their respective applications [14]. From a healthcare perspective, it would be ideal if they were based on the same clinical models, which is currently not the case. The HCIMs provided in the Netherlands offer a basis on which other standards, such as FHIR resources and openEHR archetypes, can be mapped. This approach improves flexibility and future-proofing, using one clinical model as a base.

3.3.3 Comparing SNOMED CT and LOINC

SNOMED CT and LOINC are terminology systems with different purposes and structures. Despite their different focus, the two standards have some overlap. Regenstrief and SNOMED International have signed an agreement to combine the LOINC and SNOMED CT terminology systems nationally and internationally [53].

3.3.4 Relation between the standards

Figure 5 illustrates the relation between the introduced standards. The 'Exchange and Workflow' circle includes messaging and document standards primarily focused on data exchange and clinical workflows. HL7 v2 and CDA are legacy standards commonly used for healthcare data exchange and clinical documents. Although not the focus of this thesis, they are included here for context. The domain 'Clinical Models and Persistent Data' covers standards concerned with structured clinical data modeling and long-term data storage, which includes openEHR. The area 'Clinical Terminology' contains standardized vocabularies and code systems like SNOMED CT and LOINC. Furthermore, FHIR is positioned between 'Exchange and Workflow' and 'Clinical Models and Persistent Data', supporting interoperability through exchange and structured clinical data. HCIMs overlap between 'Clinical Models and Persistent Data' and 'Clinical Terminology', with their role of defining clinical concepts linked to standardized terminologies.

Figure 5: Relation between standards HL7 v2/CDA, FHIR, openEHR, HCIMs, SNOMED CT and LOINC. Adapted from Igor Schoonbrood [51].

4 Using CQL for a different purpose: Identifying a framework for evaluating HCIMs with CQL

4.1 Introduction

CQL offers seamless integration with FHIR and provides a standardized, interoperable, and reusable approach to expressing clinical logic. In this chapter, we propose to use CQL for evaluating the implementation of HCIMs in practice. This approach is identified and captured in a framework by exploring CQL's ability to evaluate such implementations. The main idea of this approach is to analyze whether the data elements in the chosen population are correctly represented according to the HCIM agreements. The question guiding this chapter is: "How can a framework be formulated to apply CQL for evaluating the implementation of HCIMs in practice?" This question is answered by exploring the suitability of CQL for this purpose, defining two use scenarios, and a test specification method. How the framework works is illustrated with two examples.

CQL

CQL is an HL7 language standard that provides the expression of clinically focused logic that is human-readable yet structured enough for electronic processing [8]. It was developed as part of the Clinical Quality Framework (CQF) Initiative, which aims to harmonize standards for Clinical Decision Support (CDS) and Clinical Quality Measurement (CQM) [8]. Writing CQL involves creating multiple distinct expressions that query clinical data artifacts [8]. These expressions can use a wide range of operators and filters to refine the data before producing a result. CQL is organized into libraries, a collection of CQL expressions that are reusable in different healthcare settings. One of the key strengths of CQL is its independence from any specific data model, which allows it to be applied flexibly in various healthcare data environments. By separating logic from metadata and data structure, CQL enables more consistent and reusable artifact creation.

4.2 Methods

The identification of a structured, reusable framework for evaluating HCIMs with CQL was divided into several steps. First, the suitability of CQL to support the evaluation of HCIMs was analyzed. Next, two usage scenarios were defined to contextualize how the framework could be applied in practice. Third, the evaluation was framed, defining how and where the data is tested in this approach. Furthermore, a structured method was developed for the specification of CQL tests within this approach, including the output that the test should generate. Finally, two scenarios were defined to guide the use of the framework in different evaluation contexts. These scenarios were illustrated with concrete test examples to demonstrate how the framework can be used in practice.

4.2.1 Suitability of CQL for assessing correspondence to HCIM agreements

During a review of the CQL specifications, the extent to which HCIM agreements can be tested was assessed. This was based on the agreements named in Section 4.2.1.

HCIM agreements Within an HCIM, agreements are made about the following components [42]:

- **Definition:** Definition and description of the healthcare concept that is described with the HCIM.
- **The data elements, their cardinality, and their interrelationships:** The structure of the HCIM is composed of related (healthcare) data elements and their definitions, the cardinality of each data element, and the relationships between the data elements within the HCIM and between different HCIMs.
- **data type and value range of each data element:** The data type of each data element, along with the corresponding standard, and the value range of each data element.

Cardinality The cardinality of a data element indicates whether and how often a data element may or must occur in an instance. A table containing cardinalities that can occur in an HCIM is included in Appendix A.1.

Data types The following data types can be specified in an HCIM: Boolean (BL), Concept Descriptions (CD), Codable Original (CO), Instance Identifier (II), Physical Quantity (PQ), String (ST), Time Stamp (TS), Encoded Data (ED), Integer Number (INT) [42]. A more extensive description of these data types can be found in Appendix A.2.

Value sets Value sets are used for data types CD and CO, defining data element options [42]. A value set is a specific selection of codes taken from one or more code systems, used for a particular purpose.

4.2.2 Scenarios for using CQL to evaluate an HCIM

Two main scenarios were formulated to guide the practical use of the framework. Both scenarios were meant to test correspondence to HCIM agreements, but with a different goal.

HCIM compliance The implementation model can help assess the extent to which HCIMs are implemented in practice, that is, with all concepts and their mutual relationships, all data elements, and designated value sets [42, 54]. HCIM compliance is the extent to which processes and systems (software) are developed and implemented to achieve the goal of HCIMs (interoperability and reuse of health information) and correspond to the specifications and the intended implementation of HCIMs [55, 54]. An information system is fully HCIM compliant if it can enter, store, share, and display healthcare data following the specification of the HCIM, achieving interoperability and reuse of information. That means for a given HCIM, the system must [55]:

- include all required data elements and adhere to the definitions of those data elements,
- maintain all defined relationships between the data elements,
- use the correct data types for each data element,
- and follow the value sets defined by the HCIM.

There is a lack of HCIM compliance when something goes wrong somewhere in the implementation process. Problems can arise when agreements are untraceable, unclear, or still need to be developed [54]. This can involve agreements on how HCIMs should be developed, how they are applied in information standards, how the standards should be implemented in the systems, or how the systems should be used by end users [54].

4.2.3 Evaluation focus within the implementation model for HCIMs

The evaluation scope was derived from the HCIM implementation model, which consists of eight stages. The determination of the scope of the evaluation was guided by the eight stages of the implementation model. The accessibility of the data played a role in deciding where the evaluation would occur, as the data is processed through these eight stages. In addition, the process of interoperability was taken into account to assess how well the system prepares data for exchange.

Implementation model for HCIMs Achieving the benefits of HCIMs involves addressing challenges across multiple stages of the implementation process. According to the implementation model developed by Nictiz, the implementation of HCIMs can be divided into eight stages: entering, storing, extracting, converting, exchanging/sharing, receiving/referencing, processing, and reusing [54]. Clinical data travels through all eight steps in the process of reusing data, from user A to user B.

Issues may arise at any stage, and each stage will have multiple issues, making successful implementation a chain-wide challenge. The implementation model is intended to support the practical implementation of HCIMs by providing insight into the various steps involved in the actual reuse of information [54].

Figure 6: Implementation model for HCIMs, adapted from Klein Wolterink [54].

4.2.4 Test specification method for evaluating an HCIM with CQL

To ensure consistency and clarity in how tests are created, a structured test specification method was developed. This involved defining key elements, which were refined iteratively based on practical examples and expert feedback. When defining what type of output to aim for in these kinds of tests, shareability was taken into account, so as not to show any patient information. Furthermore, the output also had to be interpretable and compared with an expected result.

4.2.5 Examples

Two example tests, for each scenario, were developed, based on the HCIM 'Body Temperature'. They illustrate how a CQL test for evaluating an HCIM is specified. In Figure 7, the HCIM for 'Body Temperature' is displayed.

Figure 7: HCIM 'Body Temperature', published in 2017 [56].

4.3 Results

This section contains the results of developing a structured, reusable framework for using CQL to evaluate HCIMs. The results include an assessment of the suitability of CQL for this purpose, two application scenarios, the focus of the evaluation within the HCIM implementation model, a structured method for developing CQL tests, and example tests demonstrating the use of the framework.

4.3.1 Suitability of CQL for assessing correspondence to HCIM agreements

An assessment of the CQL specifications showed that CQL can support the evaluation of several aspects of agreements in an HCIM, as shown in Table 2. It can verify the existence of data elements, the presence of certain relationships, the data types of elements, and the usage of specific value sets within data elements.

Table 2: Assessing HCIM specifications with CQL.

HCIM specification	Capability of CQL
All required data elements are included	CQL can check whether a data element is populated
All defined relationships between data elements are maintained	CQL can check parent-child relationships, temporal relationships, and conditional relationships
The correct data types for each data element are used	CQL can check whether a data element is of a certain data type
The defined value sets are followed	CQL can determine if the value from a data element is in the defined value set and if the associated code set is referenced in the system

4.3.2 Scenarios for using CQL to evaluate an HCIM

Within this framework, we distinguish two types of scenarios to evaluate the use of HCIMs in practice. In the first scenario, tests are developed to evaluate to what extent practical data is structured according to a certain HCIM. From this point onward, we will refer to this as the HCIM compliance scenario. Here, a specific HCIM serves as the reference model. In the second scenario, the tests aim to determine how well an HCIM model represents the way data is recorded in practice. In this case, the practical data is the starting point, and we will refer to this as the HCIM alignment scenario. Tests from the HCIM compliance scenario can point out if something is wrong in the implementation. Tests from the HCIM alignment scenario can either point out if an HCIM does not align with the usage in practice or an incomplete implementation.

4.3.3 Evaluation focus in the implementation model for HCIMs

The main idea in this approach is to compare the data at the point of exchange to the expected result, as shown in Figure 8. That means clinical data is evaluated at the point it becomes available for exchange, after the first four steps of the HCIM implementation model. The evaluation is focused on steps 1 through 4, creating an opportunity to check if data is properly entered, stored, extracted, and converted so that it is ready for exchange (step 5). The expected result is based on what should be entered by the user (step 1), correct storing (step 2), extracting (step 3), and converting (step 4). For the actual result, what happened in steps 1 to 4 is unknown. CQL expressions are created so that the output is a percentage, which represents how many data elements adhere to the test.

4.3.4 Test specification method for evaluating an HCIM with CQL

For this approach, we determined that CQL expressions must be created so that the output is a percentage that represents how many instances adhere to the test. The output does not contain any patient information, only HCIM compliance or alignment for a certain population. This percentage is calculated by defining the numerator and the denominator. The numerator represents the number of instances that satisfy the expected criteria based on the agreements made in the HCIMs. The denominator represents the total number of instances that are subject to the evaluation. Thus, a group of instances is chosen (base instances); this total forms the denominator. The number of instances in this group conforming to the test (conforming instances) is the numerator. By dividing the numerator by the denominator and multiplying the result by 100, the percentage of conformance is obtained.

Figure 8: Assessing implementation of HCIMs in the first four steps of the implementation model with CQL. Comparing the actual result to the expected result.

A structured approach was defined for specifying a CQL test for HCIM evaluation. The test objective is the first to be specified. This involves determining the criteria that will be evaluated within the HCIM. The numerator, the number of instances that meet the expected condition, and the denominator, the number of instances to which the test applies, must be defined. The expected result, based on agreements made in the HCIMs, is also specified. For some tests, the expected result is discrete, such as 100% or more than 0%. Other tests have a more nuanced expected result, defined within a range, based on the expected real-world prevalence in a certain population. In addition, information is provided about how the actual result should be interpreted. This interpretation focuses on alignment with the defined criteria and does not include any analysis of potential issues, root causes, or contributing factors behind the outcome. An overview of what should be specified when defining a test following this approach is given in Table 4.

Table 3: What to specify when defining a test.

What to specify in a test	Explanation
Test objective	What aspect of the HCIM will be verified with this test
Numerator (conforming instances)	The number of instances that meet the expected condition (agreements of the HCIM)
Denominator (base instances)	The number of instances to which the test applies
Expected result	The result based on agreements made in the HCIMs
Interpretation of actual result	What a deviation from the expected result may imply

4.3.5 Examples

In this section, two examples of CQL tests for the HCIM Body Temperature are defined to illustrate the use of this framework. The first one is based on the HCIM compliance scenario, examining whether the prescribed value set is used. It tests if the data conforms to the agreements in the HCIM. The second test is guided by the HCIM alignment scenario and evaluates if the data element Comment is used in practice. This is a way of testing if the HCIM represents the situation in practice. The data element Comments is defined in the HCIM, so its use would be expected in practice. Otherwise, it may be an indication that the HCIM does not accurately reflect real-world clinical documentation in this area.

Table 4: Example of a test.

Test objective	Numerator	Denominator	Expected result	Interpretation of actual result
Determine if the value set for data element TemperatureType is used	Number of TemperatureType instances with a value from TemperatureType-Codelist	Number of TemperatureType instances	100%	0%: Values from TemperatureTypeCodelist are never used by data element TemperatureType >0% & <100%: Values from TemperatureTypeCodelist are sometimes used by data element TemperatureType 100%: Values from TemperatureTypeCodelist are always used by the data element TemperatureType
Determine if the data element Comment is used	Number of BodyTemperature instances with a Comment instance	Number of BodyTemperature instances	>0%	0%: Data element Comment is never used within BodyTemperature >0% & <100%: Data element Comment is sometimes used within BodyTemperature 100%: Data element Comment is always used within BodyTemperature

4.4 Discussion

The proposed approach was selected to fulfill the idea of providing a systematic, independent, and generic way to evaluate the use of HCIMs in healthcare institutions. It supports end-to-end verification from the point of recording to the point of exchange, covering all transformations in this process. While this does not necessarily point out in which step there might be an issue, it can draw attention to an area that needs further investigation. One of the main strengths of this approach lies in its coverage of the process from recording to exchanging.

Interpreting and analyzing test results can be challenging. The output, represented as a percentage, reflects how well the HCIM is adhered to in practice. While this provides a clear and measurable result, the output must be interpreted with caution. For example, a 100% score does not necessarily indicate HCIM compliance. It only confirms that the evaluated data passed the test. Data might be lost in the process from recording to exchanging, and this is not accounted for. Data that is never captured, or is dropped because it was not in the right format for the next step, is also not tested on and thus not visible in the test. However, an indication if there is a great amount of data loss could be checked. By testing how data elements are populated and if that conforms to expectations based on population characteristics. Moreover, this approach does not cover how information is processed or displayed by the receiving system, even though that is a vital step in achieving interoperability and (re)use of data.

Tests can be executed on different populations, defining the data input, without altering the test logic or its specifications. However, the selected population significantly impacts how the test results can be interpreted, and it directly influences the outcome. When selecting a population, it is important to consider when the HCIM was adopted within the healthcare institution. This usually does not occur immediately upon publication. For tests aiming to evaluate HCIM compliance, it is advisable to select a population from a time period in which the HCIM was known to be in active use. While the population does not need to be defined during the test design phase, it becomes essential during the analysis of the results. Moreover, testing across different populations can provide valuable insights. For example, about differences between departments, periods of time, healthcare institutions, or EHRs.

For the execution of a test, an appropriate population as data input must be selected. The choice of this population raises considerations about the detection of edge cases, the relevant time period of the population, and the size of the population. Since the tests operate at the population level, they may fail to detect edge cases or infrequent issues. To achieve reliable outcomes, the choice of population must align with the HCIM adoption

period, as mentioned above. Since HCIMs are not adopted immediately after publication, only data from the time a specific HCIM was actively in use should be included. This makes versioning and implementation timelines critical when selecting appropriate datasets. For tests with discrete outcomes, size is less of a concern. However, for tests with more nuanced results, larger and more representative datasets provide more valuable outcomes.

4.5 Conclusion

In this chapter, the proposal of using CQL to evaluate the use of HCIMs in practice is elaborated, defining how this framework should be used. The following question “How can a framework be formulated to apply CQL for evaluating the implementation of HCIMs in practice?” The resulting formulation of the framework elaborated in this chapter consists of the suitability of CQL for this purpose, two use scenarios to guide practical application, the evaluation focus, a structured method for formulating tests, and illustrative examples demonstrating its use. CQL is capable of verifying the presence of required data elements, specific relationships between those elements, correct data types, and the use of specific value sets. With the comparison of the expected result and the actual result, two scenarios were identified: HCIM compliance and HCIM alignment. The HCIM compliance scenario is aimed at testing how well the practical situation adheres to an HCIM, while the HCIM alignment scenario tests if the HCIM represents how data elements are used in practice. The evaluation in this approach is focused on the process from the recording of information to the point of exchange of information. To perform this evaluation, the test objective, conforming instances, base instances, expected result, and interpretation of actual result must be specified. The output of an evaluation will be a percentage representing how many instances adhere to the test. While offering measurable insights, this approach requires careful interpretation. Test scores which are the same as the expected result do not guarantee full HCIM compliance or HCIM alignment, as it may overlook data loss or misinterpretation. Moreover, this approach does not address how data is processed after exchange. The population used in testing significantly affects results. Selection should align with HCIM adoption timelines and can provide comparative insights across institutions or periods. Although not suited for detecting edge cases, the method offers a scalable and systematic way to evaluate HCIM implementation in practice.

5 From identification to demonstration: Establishing a test environment for evaluating HCIMs with CQL

5.1 Introduction

A dedicated test environment (referenced in Section 5.3.2) was set up to discover the possibilities of CQL expressions and validate the technical feasibility of the framework defined in Chapter 4. This environment enables the exploration of using CQL to assess the implementation of HCIMs as a first step towards usage in practice. The question in this chapter is: “How can a test environment be designed to explore how CQL can be used to assess the implementation of HCIMs?” The goal is to create a controlled setting where the proposal of using CQL can be tested, refined, and better understood. Specifically focusing on a reusable setup with the use of CQL libraries. With CQL being a FHIR standard, the integration between FHIR and HCIMs is also explored. First, it is defined what such a test environment should include. This is followed by a practical configuration of those components and the development of example libraries to illustrate the use of this environment.

CQL library

A CQL library is a reusable collection of CQL expressions containing clinical logic. The CQL Library profile defines how the FHIR resource Library can be used as a wrapper for a CQL Library [57]. The structure of a CQL Library provides room for definition, versioning, and distribution of logic and generally consists of components such as the library declaration, using statement, include references, code system, value set definitions, and define expressions [58].

5.2 Methods

The test environment is designed by defining what components it should include, a practical configuration of these components, and the development of two CQL scripts to demonstrate the earlier defined capabilities of CQL.

5.2.1 Components test environment

The determination of what components a test environment should include to explore how CQL can be used in the assessment of the implementation of HCIMs was based on the developers’ guide of CQL. In addition, the environment was iteratively shaped through a hands-on, exploratory process, further identifying the necessary components. Developing and testing examples of CQL libraries was also part of this iterative process.

CQL execution Moving from the conceptual use of CQL to its execution, two main FHIR-based methods for executing CQL can be distinguished: the ‘CQL evaluate operation’ and the ‘Library evaluate operation’ [59]. They both evaluate CQL expressions and return the results. The ‘CQL evaluate operation’ evaluates ad-hoc CQL expressions, while the ‘Library evaluate operation’ executes predefined and reusable clinical logic. The input for a ‘CQL evaluate operation’ is a raw CQL expression. It is a standalone execution, without the need to reference a FHIR Library resource. The ‘Library evaluate operation’ does need a reference to a FHIR Library resource containing CQL logic.

FHIR endpoint When executing CQL, FHIR endpoints are used for defining a data source, the content (libraries), and the terminology (value sets, code systems). An endpoint is a specific URL or address through which a system, service, or device can be accessed or interacted with over a network. A FHIR Endpoint is a resource that describes the technical details needed to connect to a system, such as the URL, protocol, and supported formats. A FHIR endpoint describes the technical details of a location to secure a connection for the delivery or retrieval of information [60]. With FHIR as a widely adopted international standard for communication, also in the Netherlands, FHIR endpoints are used extensively for communication. The FHIR endpoint module allows external clients to interact with the FHIR storage module [61]. However, this does not mean that there always is a FHIR server behind the FHIR endpoint. This could also be a FHIR facade, which is a layer that sits in front of an existing healthcare system and translates its data to FHIR format. It gives legacy systems a FHIR interface without having to fully migrate the backend to FHIR. The FHIR facade queries the legacy database of an EHR system that doesn’t support FHIR and formats the data into FHIR when requested. A FHIR facade exposes a FHIR API and presents itself as a FHIR endpoint to external systems.

5.2.2 Configuration test environment

During the development of the test environment, the following open-source tools and components were used: Docker Desktop, HAPI FHIR, CQF ruler, Synthea, Dutch National Terminology Server, and Postman. Docker served as a platform to run the CQF ruler and Synthea containers, both adapted from GitHub [62, 63]. A HAPI FHIR server extended with CQF Ruler was used to support CQL execution operations, both the 'CQL evaluate operation' and the 'Library evaluate operation' introduced in Section 5.2.1. Synthea was used to generate synthetic data for testing purposes. Furthermore, authentication credentials were obtained to access the Dutch National Terminology Server. Postman was used to request an access token for authentication with the Dutch terminology server and to invoke CQL operations by sending HTTP requests to the HAPI FHIR server.

Docker Desktop Docker is a containerization platform that packages applications along with their dependencies into portable, lightweight containers, ensuring consistent performance across environments [64, 65]. Docker containers run in isolated environments while sharing the kernel of the host operating system [64].

HAPI FHIR HAPI FHIR is a complete Java implementation of the HL7 FHIR standard for healthcare interoperability and is maintained by Smile Digital Health [66]. The HAPI FHIR server includes support for storing all resources defined in the FHIR Clinical Reasoning module [67]. The Clinical Reasoning module defines key components such as Expression Logic (FHIRPath and CQL), Definitional Resources (order sets and decision support rules), and Knowledge Artifacts (quality measures and evidence summaries) [68]. Additionally, HAPI includes an embedded CQL engine that allows it to process clinical logic encoded in a standard representation [67].

HAPI FHIR describes various use cases for their product [66]. HAPI FHIR can be used to convert between FHIR and an application's data model with the parser and encoder. Additionally, the HAPI FHIR client can be used in an application to fetch from or store resources on an external server. To allow external applications to access or modify the application's data, the HAPI FHIR server can be used. Lastly, the HAPI JPA/Database Server can deploy a fully functional FHIR server to which applications can be developed.

CQF ruler The CQF ruler offers a collection of plugins tailored for the HAPI FHIR JPA server to allow the addition of custom FHIR operations and is available at GitHub [62]. The CQL translator translates CQL to Expression Logical Model (ELM), the machine-readable representation of CQL logic, and the CQL engine executes the ELM [69]. The CQL evaluator integrates the CQL translator and CQL engine and provides implementations for several FHIR operations [69].

Synthea Synthea is an open-source tool designed to generate synthetic patient data by modeling the medical history of synthetic patients [70], and is available at GitHub [63]. With a mission to provide high-quality, synthetic, realistic but not real, patient data and associated health records covering every aspect of healthcare, Synthea offers valuable resources for research [70]. The resulting data is free from cost, privacy, and security restrictions, facilitating research with health data that is otherwise inaccessible due to legal or practical constraints.

Dutch National Terminology Server The Dutch National Terminology Server is a FHIR-compliant terminology server that ensures consistent and unambiguous access to each terminology or classification it contains. This server provides standardized medical terminologies such as Dutch value sets, SNOMED CT, and LOINC, which are essential for executing CQL queries with correct code mappings.

Postman Postman is a platform for developing and using application programming interfaces (APIs) [71]. An API endpoint is the uniform locator that identifies a resource on the server, allowing clients to interact with it through API requests [72].

5.2.3 Examples of CQL libraries for assessing HCIM specifications

The tests introduced in Section 4.3.5 were translated into CQL expressions for execution in the test environment. The HCIM profiles were used to determine what data elements should be included. In the process of developing these CQL expressions, the 'CQL evaluate operation' was used. Once a CQL expression was obtained, a CQL Library could be formed and sent to the HAPI server with 64 encoding. The following constructs were used in constructing the CQL Libraries, as outlined in the CQL Author's Guide [58]:

- **Library:** header information for the library, with the name and version of the reference file (referenced by the secondary ELM file).
- **Using:** defines the data model, specifying that types from the reference data model may be accessed.
- **Include:** the CQL library that may be used, meaning that constructs defined in the referenced library may be accessed.
- **Value set:** identifies the value set that may be referenced in the clinical logic by the given name.
- **Define:** a statement that introduces a named expression which may be referenced within the library or by other libraries. This is the basic unit of clinical logic within the CQL library.

The 'Library evaluate operation' could then be used to reference an uploaded library and execute the CQL logic it contained. Eventually, the examples could also verify that the test environment functioned as intended.

5.3 Results

This section reports the results of developing a test environment to explore how CQL can be used to assess the implementation of HCIMs. The findings include a summation of components needed for such a test environment, a description of how they were configured to create a test environment, and example expressions that can be used to assess HCIMs.

5.3.1 Components test environment

Four FHIR services are defined for a test environment to include. First, the test environment must support CQL execution via either the 'CQL evaluate operation' or the 'Library evaluate operation'. If the 'CQL evaluate operation' is used, a FHIR service for content (libraries) must be provided. When using the 'Library evaluate operation', such a service may be included, but it is not necessary. Furthermore, the test environment must provide a FHIR service to store test data. Lastly, a FHIR terminology service should be included. Without it, only expressions that do not rely on terminology resources can be evaluated, significantly limiting the scope of HCIM validation. These FHIR services may be offered through separate endpoints or combined into a single server, depending on the architecture of the environment.

Both the 'CQL evaluate operation' and the 'Library evaluate operation' have parameters for connecting to a data-, content-, or terminology-endpoint [59].

- **DataEndpoint** to access data which is referred to by retrieve operations in the library. First data bundles and the server are used (if the useServerData parameter is true), and then data from this endpoint.
- **ContentEndpoint** enables access to content (libraries) referenced by the library.
- **TerminologyEndpoint** is used to access terminology (value sets, code systems) used in the library.

In addition to these services, the test environment should provide tools to interact with exposed system APIs, enabling the construction of requests and inspection of responses. Moreover, test data is required, allowing for the simulation of execution in practice, validation of the workflow of the test environment, and development and validation of CQL expressions or libraries. This can be either anonymized EHR data, if available, or synthetic data created to simulate realistic scenarios. Since anonymized EHR data is not always accessible, it is recommended to include functionality for generating synthetic patient data. This enables testing of CQL logic and the overall workflow without using real patient data.

5.3.2 Configuration test environment

The configuration of the components in the created test environment is stated in this section. It was created using open-source platforms and with access to the Dutch National Terminology Server. This setup is available at GitHub (https://github.com/yasminbots/HCIM_evaluation_with_CQL) and archived at Zenodo (10.5281/zenodo.15722807). A sequence diagram of the process of using the test environment with the 'Library evaluate operation', illustrating how the test environment is displayed in Figure 9. A similar sequence diagram for using it for CQL expression development, with the 'CQL evaluate operation', can be found in Appendix C. The user can send external test data to the HAPI server through a connection with the CQF ruler or let Synthea generate test data. In this setup, the user must send libraries manually to the HAPI server. Postman is mostly used for authentication to the Dutch National Terminology Server and as a tool for the user of this setup to initialize the CQL request and view the result. The CQL ruler processes the CQF request in collaboration with the HAPI FHIR server. At this point, the library is loaded, and the referred terminology is retrieved from the terminology server. The CQF ruler returns the result, which the user can view in Postman.

Figure 9: Sequence diagram of test environment when using the 'Library evaluate operation'.

5.3.3 Examples of CQL libraries for assessing HCIM specifications

In this section, two CQL expressions are presented to illustrate how the test environment operates and how it can be used to assess the implementation of HCIMs. The expressions are an elaboration of the examples in 4.3.5. These examples are first translated into Figures 10 and 11. The expressions were executed within the test environment to showcase their outputs and to highlight the potential of CQL for automated assessment of HCIMs. All examples are based on FHIR version '4.0.1' and use the FHIRHelpers library. Syntax compliance was verified in the earlier obtained test environment.

Figure 10: CQL Example 1 for HCIM BodyTemperature. Assess if TemperatureTypeCodelist is used in data element TemperatureType. Elaboration of example 1 introduced in Table 4.

Example 1: What a CQL library could look like to verify if a certain value set is used within a data element is displayed in the Listing 1. This is an elaboration of the example displayed in Figure 10. The library is named CodelistTemperatureTypeCheck. First, the value set that the data element must adhere to is specified. The library defines the number of TemperatureType instances conforming to this value set as temperatureTypeCodelistCount. Then the total number of TemperatureType instances is defined under allTemperatureTypes. Finally, the percentage of TemperatureType instances that conform to the value set is computed by dividing the count of TemperatureType instances using the codelist by the total number of TemperatureType instances and multiplying by 100.

```
1 library CodelistTemperatureTypeCheck version '1.0.0'
2
3 using FHIR version '4.0.1' include FHIRHelpers version '4.0.1'
4
5 valueset TemperatureTypeCodelist: 'http://decor.nictiz.nl/fhir/ValueSet/2.16.840.1.113883.
6 2.4.3.11.60.40.2.12.6.1--20171231000000'
7
8 // number of TemperatureType instances with a value from TemperatureTypeCodelist
9 define temperatureTypeCodelistCount:
10     Count(
11         distinct [Observation] O
12             where exists (O.code.coding C where C.code = '8310-5')
13             and exists (O.method.coding C where C in TemperatureTypeCodelist)
14     )
15
16 // number of TemperatureType instances
17 define allTemperatureTypes:
18     Count(
19         distinct [Observation] O
20             where exists (O.code.coding C where C.code = '8310-5')
21             and O.method is not null
22     )
23
24 // percentage
25 define validCategoryObservationsPercentage:
26     (temperatureTypeCodelistCount / allTemperatureTypes) * 100
```

Listing 1: CQL Example 1 for HCIM BodyTemperature. Assess if TemperatureTypeCodelist is used in data element TemperatureType. Elaboration of example 1 introduced in Table 4 and visualized in Figure 10.

Figure 11: CQL Example 2 for HCIM BodyTemperature. Assess if Comment is used in root concept BodyTemperature. Elaboration of example 2 introduced in Table 4.

Example 2: To check whether a data element exists, a CQL library can look like what is displayed in Listing 2. After naming the library and declaring the FHIR model version, and including the FHIRHelpers library, the number of body temperatures with a registered comment is counted. So, the number of observations with the LOINC code '8310-5', the code for body temperature. Using distinct guarantees that the number of body temperatures with a comment is counted and not the number of comments in total, as body temperature can have multiple comments. After that, the total number of body temperatures is defined, and the percentage of body temperatures with at least one comment is calculated.

```

1 library temperatureCommentExistingCheck version '1.0.0'
2
3 using FHIR version '4.0.1'
4
5 include FHIRHelpers version '4.0.1'
6
7 // number of Bodytemperature instances with a Comment instance
8 define temperatureCommentCount:
9     Count(
10         distinct [Observation] 0
11         where exists (0.code.coding C where C.code = '8310-5')
12         and exists (0.comment)
13         return 0.subject
14     )
15
16 // number of BodyTemperature instances
17 define allBodyTemperatures:
18     Count(
19         distinct [Observation] 0
20         where exists (0.code.coding C where C.code = '8310-5')
21         return 0.subject
22     )
23
24 // percentage
25 define temperatureCommentPercentage:
26     (temperatureCommentCount / allBodyTemperatures) * 100
  
```

Listing 2: CQL Example 2 for HCIM BodyTemperature. Assess if Comment is used in root concept BodyTemperature. Elaboration of example 2 introduced in Table 4 and visualized in Figure 11.

5.4 Discussion

Alphora, which maintains the CQF Ruler, and Smile Digital Health, which maintains the HAPI server, have fused. As noted on the CQF Ruler GitHub repository, all of its functionality is currently in the process of being migrated to the hapi-fhir-jpaserver-starter project. The CQF Ruler builds on the HAPI FHIR JPA Server Starter and expands it with support for the FHIR Clinical Reasoning module. With the planned integration, all these capabilities will be embedded directly into the HAPI FHIR infrastructure, thereby eliminating the need for external plug-ins or forks. These developments suggest that in the near future, it will be possible to execute CQL logic directly in the HAPI FHIR infrastructure. Firely has also introduced features that enhance support for CQL-based operations

and validation workflows [73]. The Firely Server now includes a ready to production CQL engine that follows the implementation guide for using CQL with FHIR. In this light, the current Postman-based setup should be seen as a pragmatic and portable proof-of-concept. It enables experimentation and validation of test logic without relying on extensive infrastructure. However, as the functionality of tools like CQF Ruler becomes core to HAPI FHIR and Firely, future test environments should shift toward these integrated solutions.

Initially, the CQL runner container from GitHub [74], run via Docker, was used to execute CQL expressions against a pre-existing CQL Engine. We moved to creating a CQL runner in Postman, which offered more flexibility and possibilities to align with the needs of the project. This setup simplified integration with the National Terminology Server, as it allowed for automated token retrieval and dynamic header management for authentication. Furthermore, the move to Postman also enabled the use of the 'CQL evaluate operation' and 'Library evaluate operation', with the option to easily switch between them. Unlike the CQL runner container from GitHub, which relies on its own custom execution endpoint, the use of the 'Library evaluate operation' in Postman offered closer alignment with FHIR standards and the reuse of CQL logic in standardized library resources. Moreover, standardized requests for posting test data and libraries were created in Postman, replacing the manual use of curl in the Docker terminal. The development of shareable and repeatable workflows improved the reproducibility and maintainability.

During the validation of this test setup and the generation of tests to run in the environment, the 'CQL evaluate operation' was preferred due to its efficiency compared to the 'Library evaluate operation'. It makes iterative development faster by eliminating the need to construct a full CQL Library, encode it in base64, upload it to the server, and retrieve it for evaluation. Afterwards, when the CQL Libraries were formulated, the 'Library evaluate operation' was used. The 'Library evaluate operation' is able to reference existing libraries and support reusability. How this would go in practice is addressed in the general discussion in Chapter 7.

The HCIM profiles must be taken into account during the development of tests. They provide a translation between HCIMs and FHIR and are needed to determine which fields to use in the CQL library. Correct implementation of these profiles is part of the conversion in step 4 and is thus indirectly tested. A translation between CQL and FHIR was not necessary, as the FHIR models could be directly referenced in the CQL libraries.

Moreover, the opportunities of Synthea have not been fully used. Testing HCIMs with more specific data elements requires adjusting Synthea to generate synthetic data that includes those data elements. Future research could focus on generating more specific synthetic data. This can even include the simulation of imperfect data to better reflect the situation in practice. The development of additional CQL libraries is also recommended.

By going through the exercise of setting up and running these tests, it became clear what works, what doesn't, and which technical or conceptual obstacles need to be addressed. In this sense, the environment acted as a sandbox for discovery, helping to identify missing capabilities, potential integration hurdles, and the interpretive nuances involved in applying CQL logic to real-world data. This was very helpful due to the relatively sparse documentation about CQL.

5.5 Conclusion

In this chapter, the proposed framework is explored further in a test environment. The following question was leading: "How can a test environment be designed to explore how CQL can be used to assess the implementation of HCIMs?" To answer this, a test environment was developed that brings together the components needed for HCIM evaluation with CQL. The requirements for designing the test environment include FHIR services for executing CQL, storing test data, and CQL libraries, and hosting terminology. In addition, tools should be included to generate synthetic patient data and interact with system APIs. The resulting environment, built using HAPI FHIR, CQF Ruler, the Dutch National Terminology Server, Synthea, and Postman, enables the execution of CQL. The usage of the CQF ruler in combination with HAPI FHIR might alter in future setups, as the two have merged. Furthermore, in this context, the 'CQL evaluate operation' is best suitable for library development, while the 'Library evaluate operation' references an existing library, providing reusability. Two example CQL libraries to evaluate HCIMs demonstrate how this environment supports both HCIM compliance and alignment evaluations. The HCIM profiles provide the translation between HCIMs and FHIR and must be taken into account.

6 Illustrative example of the framework: CQL to evaluate the HCIM 'Allergy Intolerance'

6.1 Introduction

To dive deeper into the use of CQL for HCIMs, the example of a specific HCIM, namely 'Allergy Intolerance,' is examined. The focus of this chapter is: "What CQL tests can be developed to assess the practical implementation of the HCIM Allergy intolerance?" The goal is to explore the practical applicability of the framework defined in Chapter 4. Furthermore, the potential for generalization across different HCIMs is examined.

6.2 Methods

A multidisciplinary working group was brought together to help formulate the tests for the HCIM 'Allergy Intolerance'. The 2017 publication of the HCIM 'Allergy Intolerance' was used because this publication was active in most healthcare institutions at the time of the working group. The group consisted of six information architects from Nictiz, all highly familiar with the HCIM 'Allergy Intolerance'. Beforehand, they were educated on the framework for applying CQL to evaluate HCIMs, as defined in Chapter 4. The objective of the group was to formulate CQL tests for the HCIM 'Allergy Intolerance', as specified in Section 4.3.4. Afterwards, categories were formed based on the developed tests.

Allergy or intolerance An allergy or intolerance describes the tendency of a patient toward hypersensitivity to a certain substance with an expected unwanted physiological reaction after exposure to the substance [75]. It is called an allergy or intolerance when most people would not exhibit such a reaction to that amount of exposure. These observed physiological changes are typically caused by an immune response [75].

HCIM 'Allergy Intolerance' The HCIM 'Allergy Intolerance', published in 2017, is shown in Figure 12. The white block represents the root concept of the HCIM, in this case, Allergy Intolerance, and all data elements, represented in blue, are linked to it. This HCIM has a container that groups a set of data elements, specifically those describing the reaction. For each data element, the prescribed data type is presented in the upper right corner. The data elements of type CD have one or more linked code lists, represented in green.

Figure 12: HCIM Allergy intolerance, published in 2017 [75].

Data elements of the HCIM ‘Allergy Intolerance’ The HCIM ‘Allergy Intolerance’ consists of thirteen data elements. Causative Agent, with a cardinality of 1, must always be recorded when using this HCIM. It is the substance or the group of substances to which the patient is hypersensitive or allergic. Additional concepts, such as the start or criticality of hypersensitivity or allergy, are also captured in this HCIM. If a reaction is recorded, it is mandatory to give at least one symptom from the SymptomCodelist. A full description of all data elements can be found in Appendix D.

6.2.1 Formulating tests

The multidisciplinary working group was divided into two groups of three people, and they had one hour to define the tests by filling in a table containing the following columns: test objective, numerator, denominator, expected result, and interpretation of actual result. After the formulation of tests, half an hour with the whole multidisciplinary working group was reserved to merge the two tables and decide to which scenario, defined in Section 4.3.2, the tests belong.

6.2.2 Grouping tests

The results were analyzed and grouped into umbrella categories with the consensus of all participants. Divisions were made based on the corresponding expected outcome and an interpretation of the actual result.

6.3 Results

The tests that were formulated based on the developed framework in Chapter 4 and how they were grouped are covered in this results section.

6.3.1 Formulating tests

One of the tests formulated for the HCIM compliance scenario is displayed in Table 5, and one of the tests formulated for the HCIM alignment is displayed in Table 6. A list of all the formulated tests is present in Appendices E1 and E2. The interpretation can be derived from Table 7 by referencing the corresponding category letter. The test assessing whether the root concept AllergyIntolerance is used at all provides insight into the general use of the HCIM and may serve as a starting point for evaluating its implementation. Additionally, the test checking for the presence of a causative agent in registered allergies reflects a key structural requirement, aligned with the cardinality constraint defined in the HCIM. Tests verifying whether a data element is of a specific data type were considered relevant for each data element, both for existing values and for those in coded lists. Relationship-based tests were primarily associated with HCIM-specific structures.

Table 5: CQL test for evaluating the HCIM ‘Allergy Intolerance’: to what extent the HCIM agreements are met in practice.

Test objective	Numerator	Denominator	Expected result	Interpretation of actual result
Determine if registered allergies have a causative agent	Number of AllergyIntolerance instances with a CausativeAgent instance	Number of AllergyIntolerance instances	100%	Consistent with tests from category B

Table 6: CQL test for evaluating the HCIM 'Allergy Intolerance': to what extent the HCIM represents the situation in practice.

Test objective	Numerator	Denominator	Expected result	Interpretation of actual result
Determine if reaction is used	Number of AllergyIntolerance instances with at least one Reaction instance	Number of AllergyIntolerance instances	>0%	Consistent with tests from category A

6.3.2 Grouping tests

How tests with aligned expected results and interpretation of actual results are categorized can be seen in Table 7.

Table 7: Categories of CQL tests for evaluating HCIMs.

Test category	Test objective	Expected result	Interpretation of actual result
A	Determine if a certain root concept or data element is used	>0%	0%: Data element is not used in practice or not implemented and data is lost >0% & <=100%: Data element is used in practice and entered data (partly) arrives at the point of exchange
B	Determine if a certain data element is recorded alongside a data element or root concept	100%	0%: Cardinality is never honored >0% & <100%: Cardinality is partly honored 100%: Cardinality is fully honored
C	Determine if a certain data element used the defined codelist	100%	0%: Codelist is never used by this data element >0% & <100%: Codelist is sometimes used by this data element 100%: Codelist is always used by this data element
D	Determine if a certain data element is of a certain data type	100%	0%: Data element is never of this data type >0% & <100%: Data element is sometimes of this data type 100%: Data element always of this data type
E	Determine if the data captured in a certain data element is before the data captured in another data element	100%	0%: The two data elements are never captured in the right order >0% & <100%: The two data elements are sometimes captured in the right order 100%: The two data elements are always captured in the right order

6.4 Discussion

When designing examples based on the HCIM 'Allergy Intolerance', the aim was not to provide an exhaustive study but to illustrate how CQL can be used in real-world scenarios to evaluate HCIM implementation. The examples are developed using a prioritized and iterative approach, rather than a systematic analysis of all possible test cases. Selection was largely driven by what domain experts and information architects identified first as relevant or feasible. This approach was chosen because a fully systematic method would be time-consuming and ineffective, given the limitless number of potential tests for any HCIM. Moreover, since we would also recommend using this prioritized and iterative approach when designing tests in practice, it made sense to apply that same strategy in this study. However, more time could have led to insights about the boundary between relevant and less relevant tests.

Furthermore, a methodological consideration arises regarding the participants of the working group. Although selecting information architects familiar with the HCIM 'AllergyIntolerance' and with the healthcare field was effective to rapidly approach the desired results, the inclusion of additional expertise could have provided further valuable perspectives. Expertise could be found in the perspectives of terminologists, healthcare professionals, and clinical informaticists. Nevertheless, this approach provided an effective process, meeting the goal of this chapter. In future work or in designing tests in practice, we would advise including a broader group.

It is important to note that expertise is required to interpret the agreements in the HCIM. Especially when looking at cardinality. The cardinality represented in an HCIM is conceptual, while the tests are based on logical cardinality. This difference is clear to people who work with HCIM regularly, but may be difficult to grasp for others.

The test cases designed for the HCIM 'Allergy Intolerance' helped surface recurrent test patterns, which can be generalized and reused. The categories were similar to the ones introduced in Section 4.3.1. While this chapter was solely focused on the HCIM 'Allergy Intolerance', the logic in the created tests can be reused for testing other HCIMs. However, it is important to note that the defined categories may not fully capture the diversity of other HCIMs. Which specific CQL tests are interesting might differ for each HCIM. They can differ significantly in complexity, structure, and intended use, and as such, the test logic would need to be adapted accordingly.

6.5 Conclusion

This chapter was focused on the question: "What CQL tests can be developed to assess the practical implementation of the HCIM Allergy Intolerance?" Through a focus group, various CQL tests were developed that reflect data validation needs for this HCIM. The defined framework was suitable for the relatively complex HCIM 'Allergy Intolerance', extending the experience from simpler examples tested earlier. The participants successfully applied the methodology of Chapter 4 to formulate tests that verify the presence, structure, and coding of relevant data elements. This demonstrated how tests can be derived from HCIM specifications and provided an initial indication of the generalizability of libraries. The resulting tests could be categorized based on shared objectives or logic structures, as described in Section 4.3.1. This showed potential for the development of generalizable tests. The examples demonstrate the practical applicability of CQL for assessing HCIM implementation and provide a foundation for systematically evaluating data quality and conformance in clinical systems.

7 General Discussion

This thesis was aimed at exploring how CQL can be used to assess the practical implementation of HCIMs. It demonstrated this additional approach to using CQL by outlining an initial framework for evaluating HCIMs (Chapter 4), designing a test environment to execute CQL tests (Chapter 5), and applying the approach to the existing HCIM 'Allergy Intolerance' (Chapter 6). This work offers theoretical and practical contributions to systematic HCIM validation. While each chapter that answers a sub-question includes a discussion, this general discussion reflects on considerations that apply across the thesis. These include main findings, methodological choices, strengths and limitations, relationships to national initiatives, implications for broader use cases, potential implementation pathways, and suggestions for future work.

7.1 Main findings

The findings suggest that CQL holds promise for comparing the agreements defined by HCIMs with the actual structure of data in practice. Specifically, the defined framework facilitates this by testing for HCIM compliance or HCIM alignment at the point of data exchange. The developed test environment demonstrates that CQL can be used for HCIM evaluation under controlled conditions. Further exploration is needed for the development of a technical setup in practice, including how to scale the approach and incorporate real patient data. The defined test development method was used successfully to create tests for a single HCIM. Although not yet applied to multiple ones, the results suggest that tests are generalizable.

7.2 Choice of CQL

The selection of CQL was driven by its strengths in standardization, interoperability, and readability. As an HL7 standard, CQL is designed to work seamlessly with FHIR, allowing it to express clinical logic that is both human-readable and machine-executable [76]. Whereas languages like Python or JavaScript require additional infrastructure and custom tooling (e.g., standalone logic servers), CQL can work directly within FHIR ecosystems using standardized interfaces and artifacts. CQL supports implementation at scale while being accessible to both developers and clinical domain experts, making it approachable and domain-specific. Furthermore, it aligns with the decision to use FHIR as a standard for data exchange.

7.3 Strengths and limitations

One of the key strengths of this thesis lies in the identification of an additional approach to using CQL beyond its primary uses in decision support and quality measurement. By using it to systematically evaluate the implementation of HCIMs, the relevance of CQL can be extended. This integration of CQL with HCIMs, both HL7-aligned standards, supports consistent evaluation, bridging the gap between conceptual models and real-world data implementation.

Moreover, the approach demonstrated strengths related to reusability, reproducibility, and generalizability. The developed framework for using CQL to evaluate HCIMs is reusable. It provides a valuable foundation while being flexible for adjustments or additions. The test environment is realized using only open-source tools, making it reproducible. This could accelerate processes in future work, as it gives a practical environment and minimal working examples. Finally, the approach encourages the development of general CQL libraries that can be reused across different settings. This supports a scalable approach to validation and opens possibilities for collaborative library development and centralized maintenance.

There are also some limitations to address. Although efforts were made to obtain anonymized test data for executing the evaluation tests, this was unsuccessful. While synthetic data generated with Synthea provided a viable alternative for test execution, it remains unclear how the use of real-world data might affect the process. Possible barriers concerning data irregularities, institutional data access policies, or technical integration issues remain unexplored. Nevertheless, a small set of real-world data was uploaded to the environment. While this dataset was insufficient for test execution as it did not include the data elements to be tested, it did allow for a small exploration of barriers, which did not appear.

7.4 Positioning among national initiatives

This work complements and extends current national efforts such as the NFU Monitor and BgZ-audit, which track the uptake and reuse of the HCIMs in UMCs [77]. While those efforts focus on adoption, completeness, and reuse rates, they offer little insight into the semantic and structural correctness of the data as defined by HCIMs. The defined framework can fill this gap by enabling automated, reusable tests that directly assess conformance with the HCIM logic, such as the presence of mandatory elements and adherence to the value set. More importantly, the named initiatives are not scalable to use in other sectors, an advantage CQL does offer.

7.5 Relation to FAIR principles

Although the FAIR principles were not the primary focus of this thesis, we briefly discuss how applying CQL for HCIM evaluation relates to the FAIR principles. The FAIR principles are briefly explained in Section 2.5. HCIMs are introduced with the aim of contributing to interoperability and reusability. The defined approach to HCIM evaluation is primarily focused on interoperability, which may contribute to the I of the FAIR principles. Specifically, it evaluates the correct use of data elements and corresponding terminology. Furthermore, we have some considerations about the accessibility, since the availability of a FHIR endpoint as a data source is not self-evident. This can be a limitation for the ability to perform these evaluations.

7.6 Implications for other use cases

CQL is flexible enough to express validation logic across different models, making it not just valuable for HCIMs but also for other standards. Other than evaluating HCIMs, agreements recorded in other models could be tested in a similar way. For example, FHIR and openEHR, which were introduced earlier in this thesis. This may especially be useful for institutions working with hybrid architectures or transitioning between modeling standards. They could need a way to check whether the data coming from different systems still meets the agreed rules you could use the same CQL rules to validate different systems. That can be during a shift from legacy systems to FHIR, when combining systems based on different models. Institutions in these situations will possibly benefit from CQL as a validation bridge across systems.

7.7 Alternative test setup

The test setup created in Chapter 5 and used in Chapter 6 was non-local, making it more representative of a repeatable setup in practical environments. However, technical complexity may raise barriers for early experimentation. As an alternative, a local implementation can be more accessible. This can be realized in Visual Studio Code (VS Code), which has a plugin for CQL. The logic would be executed locally, and a strict directory structure would be required to store the Libraries, ValueSets, and data [78]. This setup may be easier to implement since it does not require an additional FHIR server, but we argue that it would represent a possible future implementation less accurately. That is because it would then not be talking to a content endpoint, so reusing libraries would not be scalable, which we saw as an opportunity with CQL. This is why the test environment in this thesis was based on the HAPI FHIR server, extended with the CQF ruler to facilitate CQL execution. However, for experimentation purposes and getting familiar with CQL, this can be a setup to learn from. This may also be feasible earlier within healthcare institutions if it were to be carried out on a small scale.

7.8 Practical considerations/implications

This section describes things to consider when implementing CQL to use in practice, including considerations about CQL execution, FHIR servers or facades, and library development and maintenance.

7.8.1 CQL execution

In the test environment, both the 'CQL evaluate operation' for directly executing CQL expressions and the 'Library evaluate operation' for executing CQL logic in a referenced CQL Library were used. A more extensive explanation of the differences between these two is given in Section 5.2.1. The 'Library evaluate operation' can reference already developed general libraries, contributing to scalability. However, we recommend testing the CQL expressions or libraries before using them in a production environment with the 'CQL evaluate operation'. This operation is more convenient when iterations are important for the process.

7.8.2 FHIR server or FHIR facade

At the infrastructure level of the layered framework, a FHIR server or a FHIR facade provides support for data exchange conforming to standards. Many institutions currently use a FHIR facade, translating a limited subset of their data to FHIR format for interoperability. In these cases, the tests will only be as good as the data exposed by the facade. If critical HCIM elements are excluded, test results may be misleading or incomplete. Moreover, FHIR faces do not support CQL implementations directly, raising the need for a separate server for CQL execution.

7.8.3 Library development and maintenance

To implement CQL on a scale, standardized libraries must be developed and maintained between institutions. Since these libraries express shared logic (e.g., how to assess a specific HCIM agreement), maintaining them centrally ensures consistency and reduces redundant work. Already developed libraries can be referenced to test different HCIMs or populations. We would propose to create agnostic libraries, so ones that are not tied to a specific use case, data source, or implementation setting. They would be designed to be reusable and general, meaning they can be applied across multiple contexts or systems with minimal or no modification. Libraries can also be used within libraries, creating an opportunity to make a hierarchy of libraries. Institutions like Nictiz could play a coordinating role in development and maintenance, providing and updating a national set of validated libraries, as is common in digital quality measurement programs abroad. Other than developers, domain experts should be included, including information architects, terminologists, healthcare professionals, and clinical informaticists. The set of libraries could be made available in a server, which could be called an HCIM library server, with an endpoint that is accessible for healthcare institutions.

7.9 Practical implementation pathways

Based on the experiences during the development of the test environment and discussions about potential pathways, we outline two options for use in practice. The primary distinction between these options lies in where the CQL engine is located. These options are intended to inspire further exploration and dialogue, rather than to prescribe definitive solutions. In practice, feasible options may fall between these two or require additional components or considerations. Further research is necessary to shape these implementations. In the first option, CQL execution is done within the EHR system of a healthcare institution. The second option involves executing CQL within a healthcare institution, but in a separate, imported environment. In any case, a connection with the Dutch National Terminology Server is needed, as already done in the test environment. Furthermore, it would be ideal if the libraries were developed and maintained by one umbrella organization as described in the previous section. Both options are explained in better detail in the following two sections. In both situations, components are needed for executing CQL, storing data, and CQL libraries, and hosting terminology, similar to the test environment.

7.9.1 EHR-integrated CQL execution

Some EHR vendors have implemented native support for CQL operations. For instance, Epic includes functionality to execute CQL libraries, although it seems that no healthcare institutions in the Netherlands currently hold a license to use this feature. However, a systematic review was not performed to confirm this conclusively. It remains unclear if and when this will change, and whether other major EHR systems will offer similar capabilities. Figure 13 displays our vision at this option. The EHR supports CQL execution and needs an endpoint for data (FHIR server), content (HCIM library service), and terminology (Dutch Terminology server).

7.9.2 Standalone CQL execution within the healthcare institution

In cases where the EHR lacks CQL support, we would propose the following option, shown in Figure 14. Logic can be executed apart from the EHR using an imported FHIR server that supports CQL execution. This server can query the CQL library server for HCIMs, store them, and deploy the CQL logic. A separate FHIR server can be set up to serve as the data source. Clinical data is queried via the institution's FHIR endpoint, pseudonymised, and stored in this FHIR server for evaluation. Value sets are retrieved via the Dutch National Terminology Server. This decoupled execution enables institutions to apply standardized logic without being dependent on EHR vendor capabilities.

Figure 13: CQL to assess the use of HCIMs in the Netherlands, when the CQL operation is supported by the EHR.

Figure 14: CQL to assess the use of HCIMs in the Netherlands, with a standalone CQL execution.

7.10 Future directions

Regarding the possible impact of this additional use of CQL to evaluate HCIMs, discussions about this application have already led to new insights by healthcare institutions about conforming to HCIM agreements and working with FHIR. Just the conversation about what abilities the tests would provide helped to reflect on which aspects of the HCIM agreements were currently implemented and which were not. When these tests are executed in practice, these conversations will probably continue, possibly positively affecting the efficiency.

The EHDS and national digital health initiatives push toward interoperable infrastructures, which suggests that the FHIR server might be instrumental for meeting the requirements of the EHDS. This may lead to broader support of the FHIR server. As these infrastructures mature, the conditions for scaling up HCIM evaluation with CQL will improve. However, this also requires national agreements on standard CQL libraries maintained by actors such as Nictiz. Broader support for CQL execution within EHRs would also improve the possibilities for using CQL. Maybe HCIM evaluation would not be a driving force for this change, but other implementations of CQL, such as CDS and CQM could. While the results are encouraging, they also point to the importance of further exploration across a broader set of HCIMs to better understand the robustness and scalability of the approach.

8 General Conclusion

This thesis illustrates how CQL can serve as a practical tool to systematically evaluate the implementation of HCIMs, offering a bridge between conceptual standards and practice. The main research question was: “How can CQL be used to evaluate the practical implementation of HCIMs in the Netherlands?” CQL can be used to evaluate the practical implementation of HCIMs in the Netherlands by providing a reusable evaluation framework, enabling systematic testing through a technical setup in practice, and supporting reusability through the development and maintenance of generalizable CQL libraries.

CQL is suitable for HCIM evaluation in a manner in which the actual result of a test is compared with the expected result based on HCIM agreements. In this comparison, HCIM compliance, representing how well the practical situation adheres to an HCIM, and HCIM alignment, representing how well the HCIM represents usage in practice, can be assessed. During the definition of a test, the goal, numerator, and denominator to generate a percentage (actual result), expected result, and interpretation of the expected result are defined. This is now captured in a framework, which will need to be extended and revised. Furthermore, based on the experiences during the development of the test environment, we conclude that to use CQL for HCIM evaluation, components are needed for executing CQL, storing data, CQL libraries, and hosting terminology. Although a possible increase of FHIR servers in healthcare institutions is anticipated, we expect issues with the availability of a FHIR server within a healthcare institution and the ability to perform CQL executions on the server. Lastly, general or agnostic libraries must be created to ensure reusability and testing of HCIMs on a national level.

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Appendix A: HCIM agreements

A.1 Cardinality

Cardinality	Explanation
0..1	The data element may occur 0 or 1 time.
0..*	The data element may occur 0, 1, or multiple times.
1..1 or 1	The data element must occur exactly once.
1..*	The data element must occur at least once and may occur multiple times.

Table 8: Cardinality definitions for data elements, adapted from de Bel [42].

A.2 Data types

Abbreviation	Datatype	Explanation
ANY	Generic Datatype	This abstract data type is the base for all other data types.
BL	Boolean	This data type represents binary logic. A value of this type can only be "true", "false", or a nullFlavor.
CD	Concept Descriptor	This data type specifies a concept using a code and its corresponding code system.
CO	Coded Original	This is a specialization of the CD data type.
II	Instance Identifier	This data type specifies the identification of objects, such as identifiers for organizations or individuals. For example, a social security number or passport number.
PQ	Physical Quantity	Elements of this data type are physical quantities, i.e., measurable or countable values from the physical world, including their unit.
ST	String	This type is intended for plain text in its simplest form.
TS	Timestamp	This data type captures the value of a point in time.
ED	Encoded Data	This is a general type for all kinds of multimedia data. It is used for text (with or without formatting), documents, or images.
INT	Integer Number	Whole number.

Table 9: Overview of common data types, adapted from de Bel [42].

Appendix B: Specifications of the HCIM 'Body Temperature'

Table 10: Overview of relevant HCIM elements for BodyTemperature, adapted from zibs.nl [56].

Element	Description
CausativeAgent	The substance or the group of substances to which the patient is hypersensitive or allergic.
AllergyCategory	The category to which the allergy belongs.
AllergyStatus	The status of the hypersensitivity or allergy of the patient.
StartDateTime	The date and time when the hypersensitivity or allergy occurred (can be exact, or an indication).
Criticality	The potential severity of future reactions, evaluated based on past reactions' severity, exposure dose and manner, and the life-threatening potential of the reaction type. Considered a property of the allergy, not of the reaction itself.
LastReactionDateTime	The last time a hypersensitivity or allergy reaction occurred.

Appendix C: Test environment during CQL expression development

Figure 15: Sequence diagram of test environment using the 'CQL evaluate operation'.

Appendix D: Specifications of the HCIM 'Allergy Intolerance'

Table 11: Overview of relevant HCIM elements for AllergyIntolerance, adapted from zibs.nl [75].

Element	Description
CausativeAgent	The substance or the group of substances to which the patient is hypersensitive or allergic.
AllergyCategory	The category to which the allergy belongs.
AllergyStatus	The status of the hypersensitivity or allergy of the patient.
StartDateTime	The date and time when the hypersensitivity or allergy occurred (can be exact, or an indication).
Criticality	The potential severity of future reactions, evaluated based on past reactions' severity, exposure dose and manner, and the life-threatening potential of the reaction type. Considered a property of the allergy, not of the reaction itself.
LastReactionDateTime	The last time a hypersensitivity or allergy reaction occurred.
Comment	Textual explanation of the hypersensitivity or allergy (if something cannot be captured in one of the other fields).
Symptom	Specification of the reaction that occurs after exposure to the causative substance.
SpecificSubstance	More specific indication of the substance that caused the reaction (can be a substance from a group of substances).
ReactionDescription	Textual description of the reaction as a whole.
Severity	The severity of the reaction by exposure to the causative agent.
RouteOfExposure	The way in which the patient came into contact with the causative agent or how the agent was administered.
ReactionTime	The date and time the reaction occurred (may also be a partial date if the exact date is unknown).

Appendix E: Formulated tests

E.1 Tests for HCIM compliance

Table 12: CQL test for evaluating the HCIM 'Allergy Intolerance': to what extent the HCIM agreements are met in practice.

Test objective	Numerator	Denominator	Expected result	Test category
Determine if root concept AllergyIntolerance is used	Number of patients with an AllergyIntolerance instance	Number of patients	>0%	A
Determine if registered allergies have a causative agent (cardinality in HCIM)	Number of AllergyIntolerance instances with a CausativeAgent instance	Number of AllergyIntolerance instances	100%	B
Determine if the defined codelist for data element Symptom is used	Number of Symptom instances using SymptomCodelist	Number of Symptom instances	100%	C
Determine if registered reactions have a symptom (cardinality in HCIM)	Number of Reaction instances with at least one Symptom instance	Number of Reaction instances	100%	B
Determine if one of the defined codelists for data element CausativeAgent is used	Number of CausativeAgent instances with value from CausativeAgentAllergicAgentCodelist, CausativeAgentHPKCodelist, CausativeAgentSNKCodelist, CausativeAgentSSKCodelist, or CausativeAgentThesaurus122Codelist	Number of CausativeAgent instances	100%	C
Determine if StartDateTime is of a type TS	Number of StartDateTime instances of type TS	Number of StartDateTIme instances	100%	D
Determine if ReactionTime is before or the same as LastReactionTime	Number of ReactionTime instances before or the same as LastReactionTime	Number of ReactionTime instances	100%	E

E.2 Tests for HCIM alignment

Table 13: CQL test for evaluating the HCIM 'Allergy Intolerance': to what extent the HCIM represents the situation in practice.

Test objective	Numerator	Denominator	Expected result	Test Category
Determine if reaction is used	Number of AllergyIntolerance instances with at least one Reaction instance	Number of AllergyIntolerance instances	>0%	A
Determine if SymptomCodelist provides enough options	Number of Symptom instances filled with 'Other'	Number of Symptom instances	>0%	A
Determine if reactiondescription is not overly used (instead of symptom)	Number of Reactiondescription instances AND number of Symptom instances	Number of Reaction instances AND Number of Reaction instances	>0%	A